

THE CONCEPT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract:

This article provides critical analysis of scientific and methodological literature on the research problem as well as in accordance with the purpose it gives the importance of the concept of foreign-language intercultural competence.

Key words: cross-cultural, interpersonal interaction, learning ability, categories, intercultural competence.

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The theoretical understanding of the concept of “intercultural competence” is altered as a result of the education system's overall reform. In Uzbekistan, pedagogical and methodological science once believed that developing a person's capacity for cross-cultural communication was sufficient; however, this proved to be insufficient. N. D. Galskova and N. I. Gez define intercultural competence as the capacity to actualize oneself within the framework of a cross-cultural discussion, or in the setting of intercultural communication. Its construction is carried out in the interaction that exists between the growth of human cultural experience and the development of a foreign language code, whereby an individual's attitude toward the world, himself, and the experience of creative activity may all be isolated [1]. From a linguistic perspective, intercultural competence is defined by K. Knapp as the capacity to comprehend both members of one's own culture and those of other cultures [2]. A person should learn how to create an effective, mutually beneficial dialogue with representatives of other cultures and nations within this single space, as the modern political and economic picture of the world is represented by a canvas where the cultural unity of various states is intertwined and a tendency towards global integration is noted. Language acts as a cultural bridge between various linguistic ethnic communities, facilitating contact with one another and fostering discussion and a culture of interpersonal interactions. These processes of mutual understanding and interaction are dependent on language.

But language proficiency is essentially meaningless without a well-developed, accepting, multicultural worldview. As in the past, the emphasis of the educational process is on the pupils as well as the instructor. After taking into account subject-to-subject relationships, we conclude that universal learning activities are necessary to develop foreign-language intercultural competence. The path of students' personal development through universal educational activities is expanding significantly in today's society. The universal learning activities are mastered by the students, who also get new social experiences, the capacity for self-development, and an aware and active view of their knowledge, skills, and competences. The term “learning ability” has several different connotations.

The acquisition of new knowledge and skills; the ability to absorb and process new information; the recognition of the importance of education; and the comprehension and acceptance of the educational process in its whole. The activities for universal learning differ according to the educational level. For junior, middle, and senior pupils, there are different criteria. However, in recent years, the emphasis has mostly been on information technology

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fundamentals and computer skills training. Simultaneously, there are four fundamental categories of universal learning activities:

Individual. It aids in the student's self-awareness and understanding of personality. encourages the development of moral and ethical judgment.

Educative. All they are left with is the capacity to take in information, analyze it, and come to a fresh conclusion using the knowledge gathered.

Talkative. The capacity of the student to communicate with peers, instructors, and other persons is covered by this smart word. One of the most crucial phases of a person's social development is school; issues encountered there can linger long after schooling is over.

Regulatory in nature. The capacity to create a plan and then modify it in response to fresh information. One more practical skill that may be learned in school. Intercultural dialogue, personality traits of students based on universal learning activities, the cultural traits of the nation where the language is studied, and language and cultural materials that support the integration and assimilation of foreign-language images and realities of other English-speaking cultures are thus related. While some scientists view it as a unique kind of communication, others believe that teaching other languages should ultimately aim to develop this competency. A.V. Khutorskoy's definition of intercultural competence includes the capacity to engage, which is predicated on the information, skills, and abilities picked up via intercultural and communicative interactions [3]. According to N.N. Vasilyeva, intercultural competence is the ability to recognize the unique characteristics of a given culture that have an impact on how a person's personality is formed and how they employ distinct nonverbal cues based on their national and cultural values, customs, and traditions [4]. A.P. Sadokhin defines intercultural competence as a collection of personal knowledge and abilities that are utilized for a successful intercultural engagement process while concurrently employing feedback to verify communication outcomes [5]. Multicultural competency of A.P. Sadokhin is based on linguistic, communicative, and cultural competence. Several scientists also highlighted the relationship between these elements in the development of intercultural competency in various student groups. The mechanism by which high school pupils are building this competency piqued the interest of Y.B. Kuzmenkova. This procedure was investigated in professional language education by VN Kartashova. According to G. Fischer, intercultural competence is a type of personality trait founded on a serious understanding of reality [6]. Intercultural competence, according to O.D. Mitrofanova, is the link between a person's capacity to actualize himself within the context of a cross-cultural interaction and the process of learning a foreign language and concurrently expanding his or her cultural experience. Some writers contend that while employing conventional educational methods and resources for this aim, students are deprived of the chance to properly comprehend the psychology of a representative of a different country culture.

A communicative speech scenario is defined as a collection of elements that positively impact the initiation, progression, and successful conclusion of communication participants' speech activities during the speech communication process. Within the context of communicative discourse, intercultural communication is seen as a sub-situation. It has the power to affect nonverbalism, linguistic tools, speech content, and motivation in this way.

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